

PHILOSOPHICAL SCIENCES

FROM ANTHROPOCENTRISM TO NETWORKED SUBJECTIVITY: PHILOSOPHICAL ANTHROPOLOGY IN THE AGE OF TECHNOLOGY

Medzhidova N.

Ph.D. in Philosophy, Associate Professor

Department of Philosophy

Baku State University

Baku, Azerbaijan

<https://orcid.org/0000-0002-3404-3493>

Abstract

This article explores the transformation of philosophical anthropology in the context of technological progress, which challenges traditional ideas about human exceptionalism. Special attention is given to the critique of anthropocentrism within speculative realism, object-oriented ontology, and posthumanism. The article analyzes the theoretical foundations of correlations, its critique in the works of Graham Harman, Quentin Meillassoux and Ray Brassier, as well as concepts of subject decentralization. Technological challenges are considered, including artificial intelligence, bioengineering, and the digital network organization of subjectivity, all of which contribute to the blurring of boundaries between human and technological. In conclusion, the article discusses possible ethical and philosophical consequences of this transformation and the prospects for developing new conceptual models of subjectivity.

Keywords: anthropocentrism, speculative realism, object-oriented ontology, transhumanism, correlations, posthumanism, technological subjectivity.

Introduction

The relevance of this research lies in the rapid development of technology, which puts into question the traditional understanding of humans as a unique bearer of reason and morality. The correlation paradigm that defined the subject's role in philosophy is now confronted by challenges posed by technological progress. The aim of this study is to examine the potential of technological innovation to contribute to the decentralization of the human being both ontologically and epistemologically. The methodology includes theoretical analysis of philosophical concepts, comparative approaches, and critical reflection on post-anthropocentric theories. The structure of the article includes an exposition of the main theoretical approaches, an analysis of technological challenges and their philosophical consequences, and conclusions on the prospects for the development of the anthropological paradigm.

The modern era, marked by rapid technological development, prompts a radical reconsideration of traditional ideas about human nature. While classical philosophical anthropology viewed the human being as a unique bearer of rationality, consciousness, and morality, the emergence of cybernetic thinking, artificial intelligence, genetic engineering, and robotics casts doubt on anthropocentric concepts.

Theoretical Basis of Research

Traditional philosophical anthropology, drawing on the works of Kant, Scheler, Plessner, and Cassirer, sought to define the special status of the human in contrast to animals and inanimate objects. However, since the mid-20th century, these distinctions have begun to blur as humans become embedded in large-scale technological systems. The development of cybernetics, systems theory, and information sciences has led to a rethinking of the human as an information node or a biological carrier of consciousness within networks of

communication and data. Even Merleau-Ponty and Heidegger emphasized the dependence of human experience on technological tools, but it was only with the transition to digital technologies that this influence became ubiquitous, changing the conditions for the formation of identity, ethics, and ontology [5].

This raises a key question: Can we still speak of human nature as something stable and ontologically guaranteed when technologies continuously transform the very fabric of everyday life—intervening in the genome, algorithmizing behavior, and even simulating cognitive functions of consciousness? Posthumanism and transhumanism emphasize the erosion of boundaries between the human and the technological, the biological and the artificial. Humans become a mediator among various levels of reality, not the center of meaning.

Anthropocentrism in philosophy, rooted in the humanist traditions of the Renaissance and Enlightenment, long served as a methodological foundation for analyzing human essence. Cartesian dualism—*res cogitans* and *res extensa*—established a rigid ontological division in which human thought held a privileged status. Kantian transcendental philosophy reinforced the idea that the human subject is the sole source of the structure of reality, endowing it with a priori forms of space, time, and categorical thinking.

With the rise of postmodernist and poststructuralist philosophy, anthropocentrism came under new critical scrutiny: linguistic, cultural, and social practices were presented as constitutive of reality. Thus, humans were no longer just the center but the locus of meaning production—without which the thing-in-itself remains a concept devoid of empirical content.

If human nature ceases to be a privileged starting point for moral norms, we must develop new ethical

paradigms that account for the diversity of forms of being. This may require revising legal and normative frameworks and adopting new ways of thinking about justice, dignity, and sustainable development—where objects and technologies are viewed not as passive resources but as legitimate participants in the moral landscape.

Historically, classical anthropocentrism relied on the thesis that the human is a unique being capable of constructing a meaningful reality and therefore controlling the entire discursive or material world. In early modern science and philosophy, such ideas were reinforced by Cartesian cogito and the Kantian model of the transcendental subject. This position came to be known as correlations, which posited an inseparable link between thought and being—thus denying reality the status of independent existence.

However, in the 19th and 20th centuries, anti-humanist and post-metaphysical tendencies (Marx, Nietzsche, Freud, and later poststructuralism) began to undermine the very principle of human uniqueness, showing that the subject is socially, linguistically, and unconsciously conditioned. From the mid-20th century on, the problem of anthropocentrism was further complicated by the exponential growth of technology, which on one hand reinforces human control over nature, but on the other reveals its increasing independence and capacity for autonomous development (e.g., algorithmic learning, cyber-physical systems).

The contemporary challenge to classical anthropocentrism is most vividly articulated within the framework of speculative realism, developed by G. Harman, Q. Meillassoux, and R. Brassier. Despite differences in their respective approaches, all three insist on a re-evaluation of anthropological privilege. The critique of correlations here implies a horizontal ontology or the de-anthropologization of the philosophical field, in which the human is seen as one among many equally valid entities, and its dominant status as the center is called into question. Consequently, the very idea of the human-world correlation, inherited from the Kantian paradigm, is dismantled, as the world is now conceived as possessing autonomous agency—manifested in things, algorithms, viruses, and biological forms [6; 12; 2].

Technological Challenges to Anthropocentrism

In the 21st century, technological progress has brought into philosophical focus the issue of reconstructing or transgressing human nature. Examples such as CRISPR gene-editing technologies challenge the classical notion of an immutable human core. If the genome can be rewritten, then human nature—long treated as transcendently anthropological—loses its inviolability.

Networked machine learning systems increasingly act as independent decision-making agents capable of adaptation, prediction, and pattern recognition. Humans are no longer the sole centers of cognitive activity. Algorithmic processing of big data reveals patterns in digital reality inaccessible to individual consciousness. Practices like prosthetics or chip implants blur the boundary between body and machine, creating hybrid forms of existence.

The rise of technological platforms, global social networks, and virtual spaces means that networked subjects can no longer be reduced to individual intentionality. In many cases, digital algorithms select content, shape political and economic realities, while the subject becomes dependent on these network logics. In other words, the key practices of our era show that the technological environment not only extends human power but redefines anthropocentrism itself. It now manifests in multiple hybrid forms: the human remains central only formally, while in fact their status is mediated and displaced by networks and machines.

Speculative realism and related positions (Bruno Latour, N. Katherine Hayles, Donna Haraway) argue that the traditional subject—once the center of experience and knowledge—is giving way to more flexible concepts such as networked or distributed subjectivity. This "subject" might include:

- technological components (digital sensors, intelligent protocols);
- biomedical interventions (prosthetics, CRISPR, pharmaceutical corrections);
- social and cultural forms of collective intelligence (sharing platforms, wikis, blockchain) [8;9].

In this context, the illusion that all beings are merely a correlation of human thought disappears. Instead, reality is seen as a horizontal ontology where humans, animals, robots, algorithms, and even abstract data structures are agents (or objects) in their own right. Anthropocentrism becomes just one historical hypothesis, and the idea of human predominance is limited to cultural-historical or political practices.

At the same time, technological development does not eliminate traditional anthropocentrism; in some cases, it even reinforces it in a new form. For instance, many digital systems still rely on a human operator to control machines or set parameters for algorithmic models. However, when algorithms begin to generate unpredictable effects—such as stock market crashes, fake news, or unanticipated robot behavior—humans are forced to recognize their own limitations and dependence. This reveals a peculiar technological paradox: while humans strive to maintain a central role, the dynamics of networked-algorithmic processes themselves undermine this claim, leading us to speak of an era of post- (or trans-) anthropocentrism.

The idea of horizontal ontology entails a radical rejection of the privileged status of the subject. Graham Harman, in his object-oriented ontology (OOO), argues that there are no fundamental reasons to consider humans as the primary access point to reality. Technological objects—such as drones, 3D printers, and servers—interact with each other independently of human involvement. Thus, traditional anthropocentrism fails to withstand the challenge of the horizontality inherent in technical systems. OOO, developed by Harman, is a radical rethinking of the ontological foundations of contemporary philosophy. Its primary goal is to overcome correlations, the approach that holds knowledge of reality to be possible only through the relation between subject and object. According to Harman, correlations unjustifiably privilege the human subject, turning it into the central focus of philosophical inquiry.

Harman calls this the “philosophy of access,” emphasizing that it limits philosophical investigation solely to phenomena available to human perception, thereby ignoring the reality of objects that exist independently of human beings. In his key works such as *The Quadruple Object* and *Object-Oriented Ontology: A New Theory of Everything*, Harman proposes an alternative—ontological horizontality, where all entities possess equal ontological status.

Harman traces the philosophy of access back to the tradition established by Kant, in which the relationship between human and world takes priority. According to Harman, the German philosopher made a decisive move to restrict philosophy to the study of phenomena, leaving the thing-in-itself outside the realm of accessible knowledge. Harman argues that this dualistic model of relations reinforces anthropocentrism by positing the unique role of the human as a privileged mediator between reality and its representation. He identifies two main theses that follow from the correlations circle. The first is the strong thesis, which claims that nothing exists outside the human-world correlation. The second is the weak thesis, which acknowledges the existence of reality outside humans but denies the possibility of knowing it. Harman finds both positions insufficient. The strong thesis, he argues, fails because one cannot logically derive the nonexistence of X from the tautological premise that there is no thought of X outside my thinking. The weak thesis, in Harman's view, collapses into absolute idealism, as it reduces the thing-in-itself to a thing-for-us.

To overcome the philosophy of access, Harman proposes replacing traditional vertical hierarchies with an ontological flatness, in which the human is regarded as an object among other entities. This approach transcends anthropocentrism by eliminating the need to privilege the subject in philosophical analysis. A key element of OOO is the concept of real objects. Harman asserts that all objects, including humans, exist independently of one another and possess internal autonomy. Real objects lie beyond the reach of our immediate cognition, rendering their essence inaccessible. Instead, humans interact with sensual objects—phenomenal manifestations of real objects. Harman offers an apophatic definition of the real object: it is more than the sum of its parts and less than the sum of its effects. This highlights the fundamental inexpressibility of reality in terms of its appearances. Moreover, real objects can be of any nature—physical, fictional, or imaginary. Crucially, on the ontological plane, all objects are equal, whether a centaur, a family quarrel, or a quark.

One of Harman's most important theses is the distinction between the approaches of science and art to reality. Science, according to the philosopher, remains confined to sensual objects and their qualities, relying on paradigms defined by social and historical contexts. A scientist observing a galaxy through a telescope deals with a sensual image of the object, not the object itself. The real qualities being sought are not inherent to the observed object but are projected onto it within the framework of existing scientific paradigms. Art, by contrast, engages real objects. Harman believes that art

achieves these metaphors, which allow one to glimpse the sensual qualities of real objects that would otherwise remain hidden. For example, the metaphor “a cypress is like a flame” reveals sensual aspects of the cypress that are otherwise inaccessible. In this way, art becomes a means of indirectly touching a reality that is beyond rational cognition. OOO places aesthetics at the center of philosophical analysis. Harman contends that relationships between objects are built not on causal links (as traditionally studied by science), but on allusions and metaphors. The cosmos functions not as a rational system of laws, but as an aesthetic space in which objects interact on the level of sensuality. This enables OOO to offer a new model of reality in which knowledge is replaced by the creation of new objects, and art becomes the first philosophy [6].

The concept of contingency demonstrates the independence of reality from the subject.

Another representative of speculative realism, Quentin Meillassoux, emphasizes the concept of contingency (chance), arguing that reality can radically change without human involvement. Technological innovations illustrate this randomness (e.g., new viruses, the exponential progress of AI). Nevertheless, as before, humans persistently strive to centralize these processes around their own will.

In his 1997 dissertation *The Divine Inexistence: An Essay on the Virtual God*, Meillassoux reflects on the possibility of discussing God outside the bounds of traditional theological-metaphysical discourse. He develops speculative materialism and his ontology of contingency, which he terms “ethical factuality,” and stresses the capacity of human reason to understand the world while rejecting both correlations and subjectivism, along with metaphysical assumptions of necessity [11].

Despite its declared anti-subjectivist stance, Meillassoux's philosophy has a paradoxical relationship with the category of the subject. On the one hand, his concept of factual ontology asserts the absolute primacy of uncorrelated being—existing independently of human thought. In this sense, Meillassoux's project can be characterized as radically anti-subjectivist. On the other hand, the philosopher clearly seeks to restore the subject, a tendency especially visible in some of his later texts, such as *The Immanence of the World-Beyond* (*L'immanence d'outre-Monde*), his dissertation, interviews, and his book *The Number and the Siren: A Reading of Mallarmé's Coup de dés*.

In *The Immanence of the World-Beyond*, Meillassoux introduces the concept of the vectorial subject. This subject is oriented toward the contingent, that is, the entirely accidental arrival of a utopian world of justice. According to him, this subject is magnetized from the future by the utopian idea of universal emancipation, which, however, remains entirely dependent on contingency. As Meillassoux states: “What interests me is the reverse effect of this expectation on present action and on the concrete transformation of the subject.”

Considering this concept raises several complex questions. First, the construction of utopia and the analysis of its impact on contemporary humans are clearly part of ontics—the engagement with empirical facts.

However, as previously emphasized, Meillassoux's ontology must explore not empirical entities but contingency as such—that is, the conditions for the existence of these worlds. Thus, the status of the utopian theory proposed by Meillassoux remains unclear. Moreover, its inclusion in the philosophical discourse of factual ontology demands an explanation of how utopia can be reconciled with the core principles of non-metaphysical ontology.

Despite the challenges of incorporating utopian reflections into the framework of factual ontology, the concept of the non-correlation subject deserves particular attention. First, the development of a theory of the subject within the context of factual ontology appears necessary to justify Meillassoux's philosophical position itself. If contingency is the absolute principle, how can philosophical thought that appeals to this contingency be justified? Without a theory of the subject, there is a risk of circular reasoning: the claim that contingency was revealed precisely to Meillassoux may seem arbitrary.

Second, analyzing the subject allows us to approach Meillassoux's philosophy from a methodological perspective. Investigating the subject behind the proposed concepts helps clarify how this philosophy retains its claim to affirm ontological truth that surpasses correlations. The non-correlation subject in Meillassoux's work is a figure that exists under conditions of the absolute absence of sufficient reason. This subject thinks uncorrelated being while maintaining self-identity at every moment, though remaining exposed to contingent transformations.

Notably, while factual ontology aims to overcome correlations, it effectively restores the subject-object dichotomy. In Meillassoux's view, subject and object exist as autonomous series, each ontologically independent of the other. They are not in a correlation relationship, as in Kant's philosophy, where the object is thinkable only within the transcendental conditions of the subject. Instead, subjects and objects are seen as independent causal sequences existing within the regime of absolute contingency.

Causality within the subjective series, according to Meillassoux, is defined not by an external principle or metaphysical foundation but by contingency. For example, the sequence of a subject's states can be mapped, but it lacks a final ground that could be considered the cause of the entire series. Meillassoux calls this distinctive feature of contingency "a connection without connection."

The thought of the non-correlation subject in Meillassoux proceeds with the logic of a double transgression. This move entails the negation of both the content of the current givenness and the negation of the very subject that affirms this givenness. Such a double negation allows the subject to move beyond the postmodern critique of metaphysics, anchoring itself in a state of non-metaphysical givenness. The subject overcomes the postmodern transgression, which entails endless disidentification with metaphysics, yet retains the capacity to think contingency in terms of a non-metaphysical absolute non-foundation. Thus, the subject of factual ontology becomes embedded in the structure of

contingency and can sustain a non-metaphysical horizon of thought.

The principle of contingency imposes significant limitations on the activity of the subject. Specifically, it implies that human activity should not be subordinated to utopian goals, as was often the case in the programs of radical leftist movements of the 20th century. On the contrary, subjective action should consciously accept the limitations imposed by contingency and not place the future above the present. According to Meillassoux, an ideal society will not emerge through human will, but rather because of a contingent event. Nevertheless, the subject must act as if their actions indeed bring this world closer. This attitude toward utopia allows Meillassoux to maintain a balance between the subject's activity and the primacy of contingency.

Thus, the concept of the non-correlation subject in Meillassoux's factual ontology represents an attempt to restore a figure of the subject capable of thinking uncorrelated being. This subject is freed from the constraints of language, culture, and history, yet remains embedded within the structure of contingency. Its activity is limited not only by randomness but also by the necessity of double transgression, which enables it to maintain a non-metaphysical horizon of thought. In this sense, the non-correlation subject becomes a key figure enabling the connection between thought and uncorrelated reality.

Although Meillassoux criticizes correlations, he does not entirely abandon the category of the subject but redefines it considering non-correlation thinking. The human being, with all their cultural-historical forms, finds themselves in a situation where they can conceive of reality "outside" themselves—even if only in an abstract, speculative form. A crucial practical conclusion here is that human freedom turns out to be not the result of a transcendental construction but of the factual openness of being.

About technological development, this means that the human being, on the one hand, becomes an object of bioengineering and digital manipulation and, on the other, retains the ability for self-determination and critical reevaluation of their new assembly—whether it be the cybernetic body or interaction with artificial cognitive systems. One of the most vivid examples where Meillassoux's ideas of contingency and human freedom intersect is the application of genetic engineering (CRISPR/Cas9). The possibilities of targeted genome editing effectively blur the boundaries of human nature, making it designed and unfixed. Paradoxically, this situation illustrates that human essence can no longer be understood as a stable set of characteristics. Consequently, the question "What is the human?" becomes increasingly dependent on technological development—contingent and largely unpredictable.

Eradicating the Manifest Image and Reducing the Subject to a Product of Scientific Processes

Another figure in speculative realism, Ray Brassier, emphasizes the idea of subtracting the manifest image, placing his bets on the natural sciences, where the anthropic factor is diminished. Contemporary technospheres can indirectly confirm the thesis of human finitude (universal extinction as a horizon), calling into

question humanity's special status. In biotechnology and robotics, we see subsidiary confirmation: life and mind—once sacralized—become objects of modification and experimentation. The problem of correlations and its transcendence holds a central place in Ray Brassier's philosophy. Unlike other speculative realists like Quentin Meillassoux or Graham Harman, Brassier pays special attention to the radical deconstruction of anthropocentrism and the conceptual manifest image. Following Meillassoux, Brassier interprets correlations as the dominant paradigm in contemporary philosophy, based on the impossibility of separating thought from being. But he brings a unique focus: he sees the source of correlations limits in an overgrowth of what Wilfrid Sellars called the manifest image, the set of non-scientific, everyday views of the world [2; 13]. For Brassier, the manifest image acts as a kind of correlational filter through which humans perceive reality. Philosophy that continues to rely on the manifest image remains trapped within a correlation paradigm. Even radical breaks with subject-centrism, as in Meillassoux, fail if the manifest image remains, because the thing-in-itself remains subordinated to the thing-for-us. Thus, according to Brassier, the key task is to erase the manifest image and replace it with the scientific image.

In his book *Nihil Unbound*, Brassier develops the idea of subtracting the manifest image, drawing on Sellars, Badiou, and Laruelle. The main tool is unilateralism, or one-sided duality. Unilateralism, for Brassier, is a one-way relation in which the object determines thought without being reciprocally affected by the subject: "The object forces thought to think according to it... the object thinks through the subject.". Unilateralism becomes the central mechanism by which correlation is dismantled. It implies that the object acts on thought but remains indifferent to that interaction. Thus, Brassier argues, thought is ultimately a byproduct of more fundamental processes of being.

In his later work, Brassier revises his position toward the active subject. What *Nihil Unbound* offered as passive acceptance of the thing-in-itself's impact evolves into a project of social emancipation. Brassier contends that a subject aware of its own finitude can actively intervene in world-transforming processes. Moving closer to accelerationists, he proposes a concept of collective intelligence that uses scientific achievements to reshape reality. Now, the subject for Brassier is not a passive bearer of correlation but an active participant in transforming the world to maximize human potential: "There is no reason to limit what we can achieve, or the ways we can transform ourselves and our world" [2, 239].

To grasp Brassier's position, one must refer to Sellars' conceptual distinction between the manifest image (everyday, culturally and historically conditioned representations of humans and the world) and the scientific image (the result of scientific-theoretical construction). Brassier believes that modern science, mediated by technologies, does not merely supplement the manifest image but can radically subtract it—demonstrating its inadequacy and limitations. Contemporary high technologies (AI, neural interfaces, biohacking) recast humans as assemblages of functional modules,

challenging traditional notions of identity, subjectivity, and freedom. For Brassier, this subtraction process ends the self-evident centrality of humans in the manifest image, replacing humanity with structures, algorithms, collective networks, etc.

One key question posed to philosophical anthropology considering Brassier's ideas is: is subjectivity maintained under such subtraction? On the one hand, overcoming anthropocentrism seems progressive recognizing the multiplicity and equality of all objects. On the other hand, there is apprehension that dissolving the subject could deprive humans of ethical and existential grounding. Brassier argues that only the recognition of finitude (and even nothingness) enables a more adequate picture of reality—encouraging new forms of collective and technologically mediated subjectivity.

In his later works, and related speculative realism research, the idea of active collective intelligence that creates new forms of being using technological means is emphasized. Such collective subjectivity is not just a sum of individual consciousnesses: it has a network structure enabling new utopian projects—from global distributed intelligence systems to bio-digital forms of life.

Technological development can be seen not only as a force disrupting anthropocentric paradigms, but also as a space for realizing new utopias. Here we encounter transhumanism and posthumanism, where speculative realism provides methodological frameworks for assessing ontological risks and opportunities. Human nature, in this view, becomes a project in constant reconstruction. Although these authors offer different versions of de-anthropologist, they all call for revising foundational anthropocentric perspectives.

Conclusion

Analyzing anthropocentrism through the lens of correlation paradigms shows that the "human—world" configuration ceases to be a reliable starting point in complex systems where humanity is but one among many equal elements. Biotechnological interventions render human nature open to reconstruction, while digital infrastructure creates an environment wherein human subjectivity either dissolves or is masked by network algorithms. Technology, then, is a paradoxical agent: on the one hand, it continues the human domination of nature; on the other, it erodes human uniqueness. This contradiction calls for dialogue between correlation traditions and horizontal ontologies of speculative realism.

Ultimately, anthropocentrism in the technological era undergoes a deep mutation, shifting from classical "subjective privilege" to hybrid, networked subjectivities. For philosophical anthropology to advance, it must recognize that correlation models can no longer explain the plural, nonlinear effects of the technosphere. Yet a full rejection of anthropocentrism may be premature: humans retain unique features—consciousness, ethical agency, historical practice—not reducible to technical systems. Thus, speculative realism offers valuable tools for understanding the shifting status of the human in a techno-centric age.

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